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FORMULATION DESIGN AND EVALUATION OF GASTRORETENTIVE FLOATING DOSAGE FORM OF H₂-RECEPTOR ANTAGONIST

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ABSTRACT

The objective of the present investigation is to formulate gastroretentive dosage form of Nizatidine, a H₂-receptor antagonist widely prescribed in gastric ulcers, duodenal ulcers. The short biological half-life (1 - 2 hours), maximum absorption in initial part of small intestine, colonic metabolism of Nizatidine favors development of gastro retentive floating dosage form. In the present study Nizatidine floating tablets were prepared by effervescence method using sodium bicarbonate as a gas generating agent. The tablets were formulated using direct compression technology by employing semi synthetic polymers like various grades of HPMC such as HPMC K4M, K15M, K100M and natural polymers like xanthan gum and kondagogu gum. drug-excipient compatible studies by FTIR and DSC, The FTIR and DSC study revealed that there is no drug-excipient interaction. The prepared tablets were evaluated for various physicochemical parameters such as flow properties, hardness, weight variation, friability, *in vitro* buoyancy (floating lag time, total floating time), swelling studies, drug content and *in-vitro* drug release. The *in vitro* drug release pattern of Nizatidine floating tablets was fitted to different kinetic models which showed highest regression for zero order kinetics with non fickian diffusion mechanism. Out of all formulations the one prepared with combination of HPMC K4M and K15M was optimized based on desired sustained release time (12hrs) and acceptable floating properties.

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Abstract:

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Introduction:

Nizatidine is a widely used H₂ receptor antagonist, was used as a model drug which is a competitive inhibitor of gastric acid secretion and is used for the treatment of acid-reflux disorders, active benign gastric ulcer, peptic ulcer disease, and active duodenal ulcers. Oral bioavailability of Nizatidine is 70% with a short biological half life of 1-2 hours. It does not show any demonstrable anti-androgenic effects and drug interactions compared to any other class of H₂ Receptor Antagonists¹⁻². It is having applications in the field of local delivery of drug to the stomach and proximal part of small intestine and importantly in treating microorganisms (*Helicobacter pylori*)³⁻⁴. Hydrochloric acid secreted by gastric parietal cells is majorly damaging and most consistent component form of refluxate. For this reason, current GRDDS pharmacotherapy focuses mainly on minimizing gastric acidity, either by neutralizing acid or by blocking major stimulator of this pump histamine (H₂ receptor antagonist)⁵. Gastroretentive Drug Delivery Systems (GRDDS) are useful for the drugs that are having by Narrow Absorption Window (NAW) in the upper part of the gastrointestinal tract. It has been suggested that compounding narrow absorption window drugs in a unique pharmaceutical dosage form with gastroretentive properties would enable an extended absorption phase of these drugs. After oral administration, such a dosage form would be retained in the stomach and release the drug there in a sustained manner, so that the drug would be supplied continuously to its site of absorption in the upper gastrointestinal tract. This mode of administration would best achieve the known pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic advantages of CR-DFs for these drugs⁶⁻⁷.

Since from three decades, many approaches have been used to increase the retention of an oral dosage form in the stomach, which includes floating systems⁸⁻⁹, swelling and expanding systems, bioadhesive systems^{10,11-13}, modified shape systems¹⁴⁻¹⁶, high density systems¹⁷, concomitant administration of pharmacological agents which will delay gastric emptying^{18,19}, raft systems^{20,21} and other delayed gastric²². From the formulation considerations, FDDS appears to be the most flexible and potent approach to prolong gastric residence time of drug²³.

Materials : Nizatidine was obtained as gift sample from Aurabindo pharma Pvt Ltd, Hyderabad, Xanthan gum, Kondagogu gum, Lactose was obtained as gift sample from Zydus Cadila, Ahmedabad, Hydroxy Propyl Methyl Cellulose K-4M, K15M, K-100M, was obtained as gift sample from A-Z Pharmaceuticals, Chennai. And all other chemicals used in formulations are Analytical Grade.

Methods :**Formulation of Floating Tablets of Nizatidine:**

The composition of different formulations of Nizatidine floating tablets are shown in Table no 1. Nizatidine, HPMC K4M, HPMC K15M, HPMC 100M, Xanthan gum, Kondagogu gum were passed through sieve no. 80 separately. Sodium bicarbonate was passed through sieve no. 44. All the ingredients were mixed in the proportions shown in Table no.1. The powder blends were lubricated with Magnesium stearate (1% w/w) and Talc (2% w/w) and mixed for two to three minutes. These lubricated blends were compressed into tablets using 9 mm flat faced round tooling on a multiple punch tablet machine (Rimek mini press II). The compression force was adjusted to obtain tablets with hardness in the range of 4.5 to 5.5 kg/cm². Each tablet contained 150 mg of nizatidine. Twenty one formulations were prepared and these were coded from F1 to F21.

Table 1: Composition of different floating tablet formulations of nizatidine

FC	Ingredients in mg							
	Drug	HPMC (K100M)	HPMC (K4M)	HPMC (K15M)	Xanthan gum	Kondagogu gum	Sodium bicarbonate	Lactose
F1	150	90					35	79.5
F2	150	120					35	42
F3	150		90				35	79.5
F4	150		120				35	42
F5	150		150				35	4.5
F6	150		180				40	18
F7	150			90			35	79.5
F8	150			120			35	42
F9	150			150			35	4.5
F10	150			180			40	18
F11	150				150		35	4.5
F12	150				120		35	34.5
F13	150				120		42	27.5
F14	150				120		52.5	17
F15	150				120		70	-
F16	150					150	35	4.5
F17	150					120	35	34.5
F18	150		75	75			35	4.5
F19	150		75	100			40	23
F20	150		100	75			40	23
F21	150		100	75			60	3

Evaluation Of Floating Tablets Of Nizatidine:

Prepared tablets were evaluated for post compression parameters like various quality control tests such as Tablet thickness and Diameter, Hardness, Friability, uniformity of weight, content uniformity of drug, drug release and other specific evaluation tests for GFDDS like floating lag time and total floating time. All the studies were performed in triplicate, and results were expressed as mean \pm SD. In vivo studies in rabbit using x-ray method was carried out to determine the in vivo floating property of the developed formulation.

Tablet thickness and Diameter:

Thickness and diameter of tablets were important for uniformity of tablet size. Thickness and diameter were measured using Vernier calipers.

Hardness:

This test is used to check the hardness of a tablet which may undergo chipping or breakage during storage, transportation and handling. In this six tablets were selected at random and the hardness of each tablet was measured with Monsanto hardness tester. The hardness is usually measured in terms of kg/cm^2 .

Friability:

The friability test was carried out to evaluate the hardness and stability instantly. In Roche friabilator in which twenty tablets were weighed (W_o) initially and put in a tumbling and rotating apparatus drum. Then, they are subjected to fall from 6 inches height. After completion of 100 rotations i.e., 25 rpm for 4 minutes, the tablets were again weighed (w). The percent loss in weight or friability (F) was calculated by the formula

$$F = (1 - W/W_o) \times 100$$

Where, F = friability, W_o = initial weight, W = final weight

Weight variation

Twenty tablets of each formulation were weighed using an electronic balance and average weight of Twenty tablets and standard deviation were calculated.

Content Uniformity:

This test is performed by taking twenty tablets were selected randomly, weighed and powdered. A quantity of powdered tablet equal to 150 mg of Nizatidine was dissolved in 0.1 N HCL in 100ml volumetric flask. The so formed sample was diluted and the absorbance was measured at 314 nm using 0.1 N HCl as blank and the % drug content was estimated using the follows

$$\% \text{ Drug content} = \frac{\text{drug content (mg)}}{\text{label claim (mg)}} \times 100$$

In Vitro Buoyancy Determination:

Floating Lag Time: The time taken by the tablet to emerge onto the surface of the liquid after adding to the dissolution medium, at pH 1.2, temperature $37 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$, paddle rotation at 50 rpm. It is measured using stopwatch.

Total Floating Time: The time taken by the tablet to float constantly on the surface of the simulated gastric fluid without pepsin, at pH 1.2, temperature $37 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$, paddle rotation at 50 rpm. It is measured using stopwatch.

Determination of swelling index:

The swelling behavior of a dosage unit was measured by studying its weight gain. The swelling index of tablet was determined by placing the tablets in 200 ml beaker using 0.1 N HCl. After every one hour up to 12 hours, each tablet was removed and blotted with tissue paper to remove the excess water and weighed on the balance. The experiment was performed in triplicate for each time point. The swelling index is expressed as a percentage and was calculated from the equation

$$\text{Swelling Index (S.I.)} = \{(W_t - W_o) / W_o\} \times 100$$

Where, W_t = weight of tablet at time t

W_o = weight of tablet before immersion.

In vitro dissolution studies:

Dissolution test was carried out using USP XXIV rotating paddle method (apparatus 2). The stirring rate was 50 rpm. 0.1 N hydrochloric acid was used as dissolution medium (900ml). It was maintained at $37 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. Samples of 5ml were withdrawn at predetermined time intervals, filtered and replaced with 5ml of fresh dissolution medium. The collected samples were suitably diluted with dissolution fluid, wherever necessary and were analyzed for the Nizatidine at 314 nm by using a double beam UV spectrophotometer. Each dissolution study was performed for three times and the mean values were reported.

In vivo assessment of buoyancy by using radiographic studies:

The study was performed in rabbits and it is approved by Institutional animal ethics committee. For this study the tablets were prepared by replacing the amount of drug with barium sulphate. The rabbits were allowed for free access to water prior to study. After overnight fasting of rabbits ($n=3$) tablets were administered orally. Radiographs were obtained at 1 hr, 2 hr, 4hr and 6 hr.

Results and discussion:

Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopic studies (FTIR):

Figure 1: FTIR spectra of Nizatidine

Figure 2: FTIR spectra of HPMC K4M

Figure 3: FTIR spectra of HPMC K15M

Figure 4 : FTIR spectra of Nizatidine, HPMC K4M, HPMC K15M (optimized formulation)

Figure 5 :FTIR spectra of Xanthan gum

Figure 6 :FTIR spectra of Nizatidine,Xanthan gum,

Figure 7:FTIR spectra of Kondagogu gum

Figure 8:FTIR spectra of Nizatidine, Kondagogu gum,

Differential scanning calorimetric study (DSC):

Figure 9: DSC of pure drug Nizatidine

Figure 10: DSC of optimized formulation

Table 2: Results of Physiochemical properties of Nizatidine Floating Tablets

Formulation Code	Thickness (mm)	Diameter (mm)	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Friability (%)	Drug content(%)	Weight variation(mg)
F1	4.15±0.05	8.9±0.09	4.76±0.25	0.503	99.89±1.75	349.6±1.17
F2	4.15±0.03	8.9±0.1	5.23±0.25	0.543	99.93±2.71	350±1.13
F3	4.2±0.04	8.8±0.15	6.16±0.28	0.488	102.63±2.1	349.8±0.78
F4	4.16±0.036	8.9±0.11	5.03±0.05	0.644	99.56±0.75	349.8±0.73
F5	4.19±0.025	8.9±0.05	5.06±0.11	0.488	99.96±0.56	349.7±1.08
F6	4.25±0.025	8.9±0.11	5±0.2	0.689	98.5±1.00	399.8±0.8
F7	4.17±0.092	8.9±0.05	5.16±0.35	0.472	101.7±1.60	350.05±1.14
F8	4.2±0.025	8.8±0.11	5.83±0.28	0.644	101.51±0.75	349.85±1.11
F9	4.03±0.134	8.9±0.05	5.3±0.17	0.555	102.03±1.5	350±0.62
F10	4.32±0.39	8.9±0.17	4.66±0.28	0.687	99±0.54	399.9±1.11
F11	4±0.20	9.03±0.11	5.33±0.28	0.517	98.1±1.21	349.9±1.16
F12	4.1±0.108	8.9±0.05	5.23±0.25	0.538	98.26±0.8	349.9±0.5
F13	4.15±0.15	8.9±0.11	5.16±0.28	0.661	99.4±1.01	350±0.99
F14	4.18±0.02	9±0.1	5.33±0.28	0.743	99.93±0.51	350±0.72
F15	4.12±0.18	8.9±0.1	4.83±0.28	0.593	100.66±1.74	349.4±1.21
F16	4.13±0.15	9±0.05	4.93±0.11	0.484	98.9±0.45	349.9±1.11
F17	4.1±0.03	8.9±0	5±0.2	0.638	100.46±0.96	349.6±0.98

F18	4.2±0.31	8.83±0.05	5.33±0.28	0.592	103.03±0.45	349.17±1.48
F19	4.2±0.31	9±0	4.83±0.28	0.76	99.7±1.31	399.75±0.98
F20	4.2±0.09	8.93±0.05	4.66±0.28	0.561	102.83±0.35	399.6±1.02
F21	4..25±0.09	8.93±0.05	5.5±0.3	0.503	98.6±1.4	398.9±1.39

Table 3 : Results of *In vitro* Buoyancy study of Nizatidine Floating Tablets

Formulation code	Buoyancy Lag Time (sec)	Total Floating Time (hrs)
F1	140	8
F2	190	>12
F3	88	6
F4	82	>8
F5	95	>12
F6	110	>12
F7	90	6
F8	82	>8
F9	104	>12
F10	195	>12
F11	756	>24
F12	540	>16
F13	375	>12
F14	268	>12
F15	240	>12
F16	140	>12
F17	105	>12

F18	98	>12
F19	150	>12
F20	110	>12
F21	100	>12

Table 4: Swelling index of formulations with HPMC K4M and HPMC K 15 M

Time (hr)	HPMC K4M				HPMC K15M			
	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	60	62.85	68.5	75	61.42	70	71.4	97.5
2	91.4	94.28	102.85	107.5	92.85	88.57	97.1	115
3	110	111.42	115.71	127.5	111.71	108.57	111.4	141.25
4	120	127.14	151.42	151	122.85	142.85	138.57	153.75
5	102.8	135.14	156.57	155.2	129.14	151.42	158.57	157.5
6	88.57	149.71	175.71	170	134.28	160	168.57	187.5
7	71.42	165.71	186.85	202.5	148.57	174.28	187.4	225
8		151.42	202.85	230	167.71	188.28	211.4	242.5
9		138.57	217.14	251.75	178.57	214.28	251.42	290
10			242.85	265		227.14	260	295
11			221.42	275		211.42	271.42	300
12				257.5			262.85	292.5

Table 5: Swelling index of formulations with HPMC K100M, Xanthan gum and kondagogu gum

HPMC K100M	Xanthan gum	Kondagogu gum
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Time (hr)	F1	F2	F11	F12	F13	F14	F15	F16	F17
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	60	75.71	94.28	80	82.85	86.28	90	81.42	87.14
2	91.4	105.7	122.85	111.42	104.28	105.71	110	92	97.14
3	110	129.71	140.0	137.14	134.28	137.14	140	100.85	105.7
4	128.57	137.14	160	162.85	161.42	159.14	164.28	112	114.28
5	140	152	170.57	182.8	184.28	185.71	187.14	124.28	128.57
6	155.71	164	181.71	188	191.42	198.57	202.85	136.28	137.4
7	168.57	180.28	205.71	208.5	214.28	217.14	220	140.57	142.8
8	180.57	191.71	225.71	242.8	248.57	245.71	240	157.14	158
9	192.85	204.28	245.71	260	262.85	251.42	246.28	164.28	177.14
10	215.42	220	265.71	265.7	268.57	270.85	268.57	168.57	190
11	214.28	234.28	277.14	271.4	274.28	275.71	271.42	177.14	174.2
12	-	251.42	288.57	260	265.71	271.42	280	188.57	162.8

Table 6: Swelling index of formulations with combination of HPMC K4M and HPMC K15M

Time(hr)	F18	F19	F20	F21
0	0	0	0	0
1	71.4	74	67.5	80
2	94.28	97.5	93.75	87.5
3	120	130	125	121.25
4	142.8	146.25	142.5	143.75
5	174.28	170	153.5	156.25
6	186.57	187.5	185	190
7	208.57	210	200	206.25
8	228.5	223.7	220	221.25
9	237.14	235	230	235
10	211.7	246.5	232.5	238.75
11	185.7	252.5	247.5	252.5
12	171.24	242.5	225	235

Table 7 : Invitro drug release of Nizatidine from formulations with HPMC K100M

Time(min)	Formulation code	
	F 1	F 2
0	0	0
60	19.85±0.377	16.55±0.75
120	29.5±0.75	27.58±0.38
180	35.86±0.38	36.69±0.76
240	41.76±0.532	41.89±0.83
300	49.29±0.988	48.51±0.615
360	56.86±1.3	55.39±0.47

420	61.77±1.0	63.94±0.85
480	71.86±1.66	74.59±1.63
540	79±1.31	80.45±0.28
600	93.06±1.42	86.67±0.583
660	99.58±0.29	92.86±0.74
720		95.51±0.54

Table 8 : In vitro drug release profile of Nizatidine from formulations with HPMC K4M

Time (min)	Formulation code			
	F3	F4	F5	F6
0	0	0	0	0
60	58.05±0.75	44.1±0.39	39.7±0.45	31.1±0.9
120	66.77±0.45	50.24±0.37	43.47±0.82	35.01±0.382
180	77.24±0.83	55.92±0.67	58.16±0.68	44.81±0.66
240	90.22±0.54	64.83±0.68	68.43±0.69	51.15±0.291
300	95.61±0.68	71.54±0.91	74.03±1.47	59.09±0.6
360	97.33±0.69	78.83±1.51	79.61±0.85	63.42±0.75
420	102.01±0.39	83.70±0.87	83.44±0.85	68.55±0.56
480		93.51±1.78	90.95±1.08	79.57±0.37
540		99.56±0.32	94.94±0.69	85.61±1.06
600			97.4±0.412	91.77±1.05
660			99.97±0.27	95.35±0.46
720				98.42±0.361

Table 9 : In vitro drug release profile of Nizatidine from formulations with HPMC K15M

Time (min)	Formulation code			

	F7	F8	F9	F10
0	0	0	0	0
60	47.1±0.6	38.5±0.52	34.5±0.6	28.1±0.82
120	56.66±0.45	48.91±0.53	43.24±0.905	33.6±0.45
180	58.87±0.68	55.28±0.53	45.38±0.76	38.58±0.605
240	65.5±0.53	61.09±1.14	52.53±0.53	44.75±0.455
300	75.61±0.45	65.97±0.69	58.96±1.21	49.64±0.836
360	82.22±0.74	68.98±0.46	62.94±1.45	57.49±0.94
420	91.21±0.54	72.66±0.47	69.93±0.49	59.49±0.77
480	96.16±1.66	86.3±1.3	79.78±0.75	64.46±0.85
540	99.58±0.47	91.97±0.63	87.89±1.01	73.32±1.46
600		97.96±0.49	93.07±0.86	80.24±0.49
660		101.39±0.53	97.17±0.63	89.44±0.35
720			101.89±0.41	96.18±1.04

Table 10: In vitro drug release profile of Nizatidine from formulations with combination of HPMC K4M and HPMC K15M

Time (min)	Formulation code			
	F18	F19	F20	F21
0	0	0	0	0
60	34.6±0.826	18.09±0.83	24.75±0.6	29.55±0.45
120	44.08±0.372	29.34±0.6	31.63±0.75	35±0.531
180	51.83±0.377	34.7±1.13	40.05±0.46	50.2±0.38
240	58.31±0.305	46.99±0.66	46.22±0.52	59.58±0.44
300	60.93±0.773	50.8±0.67	52.83±0.39	61.95±1.357
360	67.82±0.46	56.33±0.44	60.57±1.02	70.99±1.41
420	77.54±0.76	60.12±0.37	65.5±0.75	76.13±0.462
480	90.66±0.47	64.27±2.25	71.5±0.53	78.44±1.94
540	96.85±1.15	73.82±0.62	78.29±1.12	83.06±0.685
600	98.83±0.347	79.51±0.69	85.51±0.4	93.85±1.345
660	99.87±0.985	89.74±2.15	92.73±0.61	99.67±0.9
720	102.94±0.376	94.07±0.51	98.03±0.3	102.8±0.22

Table 11: In vitro drug release profile of Nizatidine from formulations with xanthan gum and kondagogu gum

Time (min)	Formulation code		
	F11	F16	F17
0	0	0	0
60	14.5±0.62	18.24±1.05	21.3±0.3
120	17.02±0.829	25.84±1.44	32.31±0.52
180	22.46±0.697	30.23±0.73	41.09±0.45
240	30.42±0.6	38.6±0.6	50.12±0.76
300	34.31±0.826	45.5±1.67	59.45±0.54
360	37.7±0.305	54.96±0.83	64.37±1.49
420	43.35±0.372	62.37±1.49	73.14±0.37
480	48.19±0.45	72.3±0.91	81.02±0.37
540	54.55±1.24	78.39±0.16	87.71±0.82
600	55.64±0.29	82.1±0.59	90.98±0.54
660	59.8±0.54	89.07±0.52	96.13±0.26
720	64.77±0.62	93.64±0.31	99.93±0.14

Table 12: In vitro drug release profile of Nizatidine from formulations with xanthan gum Using increasing concentration of sodium bicarbonate

Time (min)	Formulation code			
	F12	F13	F14	F15
0	0	0	0	0
60	15.45±0.6	16.95±0.3	21.5±0.904	22.9±0.45
120	22.88±0.54	21.48±0.372	28.26±0.37	26.27±0.61
180	28.96±0.52	26.58±0.408	33.96±0.61	32.51±0.6
240	32.62±0.68	34.1±0.6	38.6±0.487	43.4±1.13
300	42.2±0.97	38.33±0.74	43.72±0.697	48.33±0.83
360	47.23±0.37	47.56±0.6	53.56±0.58	57.04±0.53
420	51.04±0.67	53.75±0.52	58.8±1.42	63.9±0.6
480	57.32±3.04	57.49±0.53	61.27±0.606	67.75±0.54
540	62.38±0.62	61.7±0.466	65.4±1.65	72.57±0.388

600	66.27±0.706	67.99±0.54	72.35±2.29	76.61±0.31
660	71.37±0.58	74.5±0.6	79.49±0.378	82.07±0.66
720	75.61±0.51	81.51±0.38	83.32±0.612	84.62±0.305

Table 13: Different kinetic models for Nizatidine floating tablets

Formulation code	Zero order	First order	Higuchi	Korsmayer peppas		Hixon crowell
	R ²	R ²	R ²	R ²	n	R ²
F1	0.991	0.641	0.953	0.978	0.665	0.833
F2	0.992	0.913	0.984	0.995	0.713	0.968
F3	0.943	0.973	0.975	0.986	0.813	0.839
F4	0.997	0.693	0.971	0.984	0.745	0.872
F5	0.953	0.683	0.985	0.97	0.701	0.946
F6	0.991	0.867	0.98	0.969	0.508	0.954
F7	0.988	0.785	0.969	0.947	0.355	0.924
F8	0.985	0.815	0.965	0.964	0.402	0.746
F9	0.992	0.838	0.96	0.949	0.457	0.752
F10	0.989	0.799	0.947	0.948	0.503	0.895
F11	0.992	0.990	0.981	0.976	0.65	0.994
F12	0.993	0.988	0.989	0.993	0.653	0.996
F13	0.996	0.953	0.973	0.976	0.664	0.978
F14	0.994	0.957	0.978	0.98	0.562	0.980
F15	0.982	0.986	0.985	0.972	0.586	0.995
F16	0.993	0.926	0.977	0.981	0.700	0.973
F17	0.982	0.668	0.995	0.998	0.638	0.926
F18	0.97	0.807	0.969	0.969	0.469	0.867
F19	0.987	0.871	0.978	0.991	0.645	0.940
F20	0.998	0.812	0.981	0.984	0.571	0.926
F21	0.976	0.741	0.986	0.983	0.521	0.772

IN VIVO ASSESSMENT OF GASTRORETENTIVITY:Table 14: Formula used for *invivo* studies

Ingredient	Weight in mg
Barium sulphate	30
HPMC K4M	30
HPMC K 15M	30

Sodium bicarbonate	10
Magnesium stearate	1
Talc	1
Total tablet weight	102

Figure 12: X-ray photographs showing In vivo buoyancy of floating tablets of optimized formulation

At 1 hr interval

At 2 hr interval

At 4 hr interval

At 6 hr interval

A standard concentration of Nizatidine was prepared in 0.1N HCl and the absorbances were measured at 314 nm. Nizatidine is showing good linearity between 25-250 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ with a correlation coefficient of 0.999. The floatation was accomplished by incorporating gas generating agent, sodium bicarbonate into a swellable polymer.

FTIR and DSC studies of the pure drug Nizatidine and formulations showed that there was no drug polymer interaction.

Floating matrix tablets were formulated by using semi synthetic polymers such as HPMC K4M, HPMC K15M, HPMC K100M and natural polymers like Xanthan gum, Kondagogu gum.

The physico chemical properties of all the formulations were found to be within the prescribed official limits.

Floating tablet formulations containing HPMC polymer showed less floating lag time than the formulations containing Xanthan gum.

The increase in polymer concentration and viscosity causes retarding of the drug release. Formulations containing higher polymer concentration had slower drug release when compared to formulations with lower concentration of polymers.

Comparing the three different grades of methocel (K4M, K15M and K100M), it was found that combination of polymers containing HPMC K4M with less concentration of HPMC K15M provided better-controlled release characteristics with excellent drug release and in-vitro buoyancy. To study the effect of sodium bicarbonate on floating lag time and drug release xanthan gum formulations were selected as these showed increased floating lag time. It was observed that as the concentration of sodium bicarbonate increased drug release was increased to certain extent. Formulations with Xanthan gum, Kondagogu gum gave sustained release characteristics for 12 hours. Of the two natural polymers Kondagogu gum formulations showed desired release. Formulation F20 gave better-controlled drug release with desired loading dose in comparison to the all other formulations. Hence F20 formulation is optimized.

The drug release pattern from the optimized formulations followed zero order kinetics with non fickian diffusion mechanism.

In vivo studies were conducted on rabbits to find the gastric residence time of the tablet. The floating tablets prepared with combination of HPMC K4M and HPMC K15 M were used for the study. The X-ray images showed the tablet residence in the stomach for about 5 hours, clearly indicating the good floating property in the gastric juice.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the effervescent based GDDS is a promising approach to achieve in vitro buoyancy by using gel forming polymers HPMC K4M, HPMC K15M, HPMC K100M, Xanthan gum, Kondagogu gum and combination of HPMC K4M, HPMC K15M polymers by employing Sodium bicarbonate as gas generating agent. Among the various GDDS formulations studied, the formulation prepared with combination of HPMC K4M and HPMC K15 M showed the best result in terms of the required lag time (110 sec) and floating duration releasing $98.03 \pm 0.3\%$ of the drug in 12 h and is considered as the ideal formulation. The dosage form can control the release, avoid dose dumping and extend the duration of action of a drug with prolonged floating time. The present study demonstrates that Nizatidine could be successfully delivered to provide relief of gastric acidity by design of a floating formulation, where loading dose of Nizatidine will provide relief from acid secretion after meals while maintenance dose will provide controlled release for 12 hrs. This dosage form holds promise for further in vivo studies which can be extrapolated for the development of other delivery system.

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